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COMPARATIVE STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF RELEASE KINETICS OF CORIANDER FORMULATIONS

Aditi Vats^{1*}, Pranav Sharma¹

¹D.J. College of Pharmacy, Niwari Road, Modinagar-201204, U.P.

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ABSTRACT

Acne is an inflammatory disease of sebaceous follicles of skin. The present study was conducted to formulate and evaluate the topical anti acne formulation of coriander oil and coriander aqueous extract with and without penetration enhancer. Then these formulations were compared with each other to establish the effect of penetration enhancer. The antibacterial activity of Coriander oil and aqueous extract against *Propionibacterium acne* (*P.acne*) and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (*S.epidermidis*) was investigated by disc diffusion method and Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) by agar dilution method. The topical formulations were developed separately without penetration enhancer (menthol) and further two formulations were developed separately with penetration enhancer. These formulations were subjected to the drug content uniformity, *invitro* diffusion and skin permeation studies. The results showed that coriander oil possesses greater potency as compared to the aqueous extract as the MIC values of 1%v/v and 1.1%v/v were obtained for oil against *P.acne* and *S. epidermidis* respectively. The incorporation of penetration enhancer resulted in the formulations with increased drug content, *invitro* release and permeation. The statistical analysis showed that menthol incorporation led to the significant increase in the permeation of both types of formulations. All the formulations followed the first order release and Higuchi model was found to be the most suitable one.

Corresponding author

Aditi vats, Dept. of Pharmaceutics, D.J. College of Pharmacy, Niwari Road, Modinagar-201204, U.P. India. Ph. No. 919808623380

e-mail: sh.aditi.vats@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Acne vulgaris is an extremely common disorder affecting virtually all individuals at least once during life. It appears to be simple but is chronic in nature. As per global statistics, acne vulgaris affects approximately 85% of population between ages of 12-25 years; nearly 8% adults aged 23-34 years and 3% of adult aged 35-44 years.⁵ It is perilous to underestimate its importance as it can have negative psychosocial consequences on the affected individuals including diminished self-esteem, social withdrawal due to embarrassment, depression, unemployment and even suicidal ideations. Acne is an inflammatory disease of sebaceous follicles of skin, marked by comedones, papules, and pustules.

Pathogenesis of acne vulgaris

Acne is a disease of pilosebaceous glands. Multiple factors are responsible for pathogenesis of acne as sebum, abnormal follicular differentiation, hormones, *Propionibacterium acne* (*P. acne*), inflammation and nutrition.

Harmones- Androgens have only the priming role in acne development as they (testosterone and dehydrotestosterone) stimulate proliferation and differentiation of sebocytes and infundibular keratinocytes. The hyperkeratinisation in follicular infundibulum and sebaceous duct is one of the most crucial events in the development of acne lesions¹⁴

Sebum- The severity of acne is directly proportional to the sebum production. The secretion of sebum increases due to enlargement of sebaceous glands under the stimulatory action of androgens. The sebum of acne patients is characterized by the presence of lipoperoxides due to peroxidation of squalene and diminished levels of sebum antioxidant¹². Abnormal follicular epithelial differentiation-It marks the most primary change in the pilosebaceous unit in acne patients. Desquamated cornified cells of upper canal of the follicle become abnormally adherent. These cells form a retained, microscopic hyperkeratotic plug (the microcomedo) in follicular canal. This process called comedogenesis. The progressive enlargement of microcomedo gives rise to clinically visible comedo³⁷ Bacteria- *Propionibacterium acne* is an anaerobic obligate diptheroid that resides beneath the surface of human skin and populates the androgen stimulated sebaceous follicles. The oxidative stress within the pilosebaceous unit changes the environment from aerobic to anaerobic which is the best suited for this gram positive bacterium. It causes inflammatory acne²⁸. *Staphylococcus epidermidis* is also the resident of human skin flora and is the aerobic organism associated with superficial infections within the sebaceous units²³. Inflammation- Inflammation is the direct or indirect result of proliferation of *P. acne* which may activate keratinocytes and sebocytes via TLR, CD14 and CD1 molecules. TLR2 is expressed on the surface of macrophages surrounding the pilosebaceous follicles in acne lesions. Activation of TLR2 leads to triggering of transcription factor nuclear factor and thus the production of cytokines which along with IL8 and IL 12, released from TLR2 positive monocytes, produce the inflammatory lesions of acne¹⁴.

Nutrition- Acne is also driven by growth factors (particularly insulin-like growth factor [IGF-1]) acting on sebaceous glands and keratinocytes lining the pilary canal. Dairy products contain 5 α -reduced steroid hormones and other steroid precursors of DHT that drive sebaceous gland function. Drinking milk causes a direct rise in IGF-1 through a disproportionate elevation in blood sugar and serum insulin level. High glycemic load foods also cause IGF-1 mediated elevations in DHT. IGF-1 levels during teenage years closely parallel acne activity and are likely synergistic with the steroid hormones^{14, 16}. The acne treatment mainly comprises of antibiotics given for long duration. This long term expensive treatment increases the instances of alarming adverse effects.

The increasing instances of bacterial resistances²⁹ further developed the surge to adopt an alternative treatment. Among the alternative treatments, natural therapy is the most acceptable. The natural therapy lacking adverse effects is highly desirable with respect to its conceivable safety and rare *P. acne* resistance. Naturally derived compounds, particularly those from herbs have been a good prospect for future development of anti acne products³.

India correlates the three vital fields of R&D network i.e. modern medicines, Indian system of medicine and life and pharmaceutical sciences⁵ by adopting the Reverse pharmacology and triangular research. India with all these contributing factors is heading to increase its herbal market growth rate, pegged at 12% per annum. So, herbals are one of the key areas of growth both at national and international level.⁶

A herbal formulation for treatment of acne should have the characteristics like (i) it should be antioxidant (ii) it should have anti-inflammatory activity (iii) it should have anti bacterial activity against acne causing bacteria i.e. *P. acne* and *S.epidermidis* (iv) and should have anti scarring activity. *Coriandrum sativum* is medicinally proved to have therapeutic activities like hypoglycemic^{25,32}, anti-inflammatory^{7,8}, Hypolipidemic^{24,34}, antioxidant²³, anti scarring property due to the presence of salicylic acid² and anti microbial activity against bacteria and fungi^{26,31}.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The coriander leaves and dried seeds were purchased from the local markets of Modinagar. The plant material was authenticated by taxonomist at Modinagar and the specimens were deposited at Botanical section of M. M. PG College, Modinagar. The test organisms, *P.acne* (MTCC 1951) and *S. epidermidis* (MTCC 931), were obtained from Microbial culture collection and Gene bank, Chandigarh, India. All media were purchased from Hi-Media. All reagents used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Gel of aqueous extract

The aqueous extract was prepared by cold maceration method for 7 days³⁸. The weighed amount of methyl paraben was dissolved in 5ml of hot water and propyl paraben was added on slight cooling of water. To this beaker carbopol 934 was dispersed with continuous stirring for 20 min after addition of 50 ml of distilled water. This dispersion was kept overnight for soaking. In another beaker the required quantity of propylene glycol and polyethylene glycol [PEG 400] were added. This mixture along with concentration of aqueous extract corresponding to its MIC was incorporated to carbopol beaker with stirring. The volume was made up with distilled water and stirring was done vigorously. Triethanolamine was added from the gel by adjusting pH to 6.8.^{10,15,27}

Preparation of gel of Coriander oil

The weighed amount of methyl paraben was dissolved in 5ml of hot water and propyl paraben was added on slight cooling of water. To this beaker carbopol 934 was dispersed with continuous stirring for 20 min after addition of 50 ml of distilled water. This dispersion was kept overnight for soaking. In another beaker the required quantity of propylene glycol and polyethylene glycol [PEG 400] were added. To this mixture concentration of Coriander oil, obtained by hydrodistillation of coriander seeds³⁸, dissolved in ethanol corresponding to its MIC²² was also incorporated and finally this mixture was added to the carbopol beaker with stirring. The volume was made up with distilled water and stirring was done vigorously. Triethanolamine was added from the gel by adjusting pH to 6.8.^{10,15,27}

Determination of antibacterial activity of coriander extract and coriander oil

Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity was determined by disc diffusion method. This experiment was performed by following the method of Hayes and Markovic (2002) with some modifications. *P. acne* was incubated in ASLA agar medium for 48 hrs under anaerobic conditions and adjusted to yield approximately 1×10^8 CFU/ml. The agar plates were swabbed by with inoculums. 0.05% polysorbate 80 was added to the agar base used for coriander oil. The sterile filter paper disc of diameter 6mm were aseptically placed on the inoculated plates and were impregnated with the test material (100mg/ml of extracts and 20 μ l of coriander oil). The plates were left at ambient temperature for 30 min to allow exceed pre diffusion prior to incubation at 37 °C for 72 hrs under anaerobic conditions in a anaerobic bag (Hi-Media) with gas pack and indicator tablets and the bag was kept in

Table 1: Antimicrobial activity of coriander extract and oil

S.No.	Test Sample	Zone Of Inhibition (mm)		MIC	
		<i>P. acne</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>P. acne</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>
		Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D
1.	Aqueous extract	21.5 \pm 1.4	20.6 \pm 1.09	1.7 mg/ml	2.1 mg/ml
2.	Coriander Oil	31.4 \pm 2.5	28.1 \pm 2.4	1 % v/v	1.1 % v/v

Table 2: Antibacterial activity of formulations

Formulations	Zone of inhibition(mm),mean \pm SD	
	<i>P. acne</i>	<i>S.epidermidis</i>
Fa ₁	21.5 \pm 1.2	20.6 \pm 1.06
Fa ₁₁	21.7 \pm 2.4	20.8 \pm 2.06
FO ₁	31.4 \pm 2.4	28.1 \pm 2.06
FO ₁₁	31.6 \pm 2.2	28.8 \pm 2.05
Clindamycin phosphate	31.7 \pm 2.4	30.2 \pm 2.1

an incubator for 72 hrs at 37 + 1 °C . Gas packs containing citric acid, sodium carbonate and sodium borohydride were used to maintain and check the anaerobiosis. The indicator tablet of methylene blue changed from dark pink-blue-light pink finally, which indicated the achievement of anaerobic condition. The culture of *S. epidermidis* was prepared in nutrient agar medium at 24 hrs under aerobic conditions. Test samples of this aerobic bacterium were incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs under aerobic conditions. The anti bacterial activity was

estimated by measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition. All disc diffusion tests were performed in three separate experiments and antibacterial activity was expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation.^{19,20,22}

Table 3: Permeation Data of formulations

Form	D.con(%m/m)	%C.rel(diffusion)	%C.rel (perm)	J($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{hr}^{-1}$) ^a	K _p ($\text{cm} \cdot \text{hr}^{-1} \cdot 10^3$) ^a	E.R
Fa ₁	94.5 \pm 2.15	91 \pm 1.9	90 \pm 1.49	44.6 \pm 1.05	1.93 \pm 0.01	1
Fa ₁₁	97.9 \pm 2.6	96.8 \pm 2.3	95.8 \pm 2.61	74.4 \pm 2.09	3.23 \pm 0.03	1.67
Fo ₁	96.5 \pm 2.91	92.1 \pm 2.12	91.5 \pm 1.93	49.6 \pm 1.09	3.81 \pm 0.04	1
Fo ₁₁	98.9 \pm 3.26	98.2 \pm 2.76	97.7 \pm 2.8	85.8 \pm 2.2	6.6 \pm 0.06	1.73

a = mean \pm standard deviation. All experiments were performed in triplicate. Form: Formulations, D.con: Drug content, C.rel: Cumulative release, Perm: permeation, E.R: Enhancement ratio, J: Flux, K_p: permeability coefficient

Table 4: Release Kinetic parameters for formulations.

Form	Zero order model		First order model		Higuchi model	
	R ²	K ₀ (min ⁻¹)	R ²	K ₁ (min ⁻¹)	R ²	K _H (min ^{-1/2})
Fa ₁	0.9686	0.684	0.9776	0.0036	0.9995	9.489
Fa ₁₁	0.9565	0.814	0.9607	0.0038	0.9989	9.9544
Fo ₁	0.9565	0.814	0.9767	0.0039	0.9989	9.9544
Fo ₁₁	0.9574	0.7043	0.9602	0.0037	0.999	9.74

Determination of Minimum inhibitory Concentration

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values were determined by agar dilution method. The test materials were added aseptically to 20ml aliquots of sterile molten agar (containing 0.05% polysorbate 80 in case of coriander oil) at appropriate range of test material (0.05mg/ml- 5mg/ml for extract and 0.05- 3% v/v for coriander oil). The resulting agar solutions were vortexed at high speed for 15 secs or until completely dispersed, immediately poured into sterile petri plates then allowed to set for 30 min. The plates were then inoculated with the *P. acne*. The inoculated plates were left until the inoculums had set and then incubated under anaerobic conditions at 37⁰C for 72 hrs in gas bag (Hi-Media) with gas pack and indicator tablets and the bag was kept in an incubator for specified duration at specified temperature. Gas packs containing citric acid, sodium carbonate and sodium borohydride were used to maintain and check the anaerobiosis. The indicator tablet of methylene blue changed from dark pink-blue-light pink finally, which indicated the achievement of anaerobic condition. The test samples of *S. epidermidis* were prepared in nutrient agar medium and incubated for 24 hrs at 37⁰C under aerobic conditions. Following the incubation period, the plates were observed and recorded for the presence or absence of growth. From the results, MIC was recorded as the lowest concentration of test substance where the absence of growth was observed^{22,29,30}.

Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined by subculturing the samples on to the sterile agar plates from the three test plates, with each of bacterium, which had shown no growth during the determination of MIC. The plates for each of bacterium were incubated following the same procedure as described in MIC determination. The minimum bactericidal concentration values were interpreted as the highest dilution (lowest concentration) of sample which showed no growth on agar plates^{22,29,30}.

A

B

C

Fig 4: Release Kinetic model for optimized formulation of coriander extract.

A: Fa₁ Zero order release kinetic model, B: Fa₁ First order release kinetic model, C: Fa₁ Higuchi model.

Antimicrobial studies of the formulations-

The solutions of the gels were prepared using 100mg of gel in 10ml of dimethyl sulfoxide. The anti bacterial activity was tested by well diffusion method. *P. acne* was incubated in ASLA agar medium for 48 hrs under anaerobic conditions and adjusted to yield approximately 1×10^8 CFU/ml. The solidified agar plates were swabbed with inoculums on the surface. The equidistance wells were cut in the plates with help of 8mm borer. In each of these wells the gel solutions were placed and the plates were left at ambient temperature for 30 min to allow pre diffusion prior to incubation at 37 °C for 72 hrs under anaerobic conditions in a anaerobic bag (Hi-

Media) with gas pack and indicator tablets and the bag was kept in an incubator for 72 hrs at 37 ± 1 °C. Gas packs containing citric acid, sodium carbonate and sodium borohydride were used to maintain and check the anaerobiosis. The indicator tablet of methylene blue changed from dark pink-blue-light pink finally, which indicated the achievement of anaerobic condition. The culture of *S. epidermidis* was prepared in nutrient agar medium at 24 hrs under aerobic conditions. Test samples of this aerobic bacterium were incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs under aerobic conditions. The anti bacterial activity was estimated by measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition. All well diffusion tests were performed in three separate experiments and antibacterial activity was expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation ¹.

Drug Content

The drug content of the gel formulations was determined by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity 1gm of gel in 100ml of solvent (phosphate buffer pH 6.8 for formulations of aqueous extract of coriander and a mixture of ethanol and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (60:40) for formulations of coriander oil). The solutions were kept for shaking for 4 hrs and then kept for 6 hrs for complete dissolution of the formulations. Then the solutions were filtered through 0.45mm membrane filters and proper dilutions were made and solutions were subjected to the Spectrophotometric analysis. The drug content was calculated from the linear regression equation obtained from the calibration data.

In-vitro diffusion studies

The in-vitro diffusion studies for all formulations were carried out using the Franz diffusion cell with an area of 3.7994 cm² and 100cm height, having a diffusion area of 3.8 cm². A weighed quantity of formulation equivalent to 1g of the drug was placed onto the dialysis membrane-70 (Hi-Media) and was immersed slightly in 100ml of receptor medium (phosphate buffer pH6.8 for the formulations of coriander aqueous extract and mixture of ethanol: phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (60:40) for the formulations of coriander oil) which was continuously stirred and the temperature was maintained at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Aliquots of 1ml were withdrawn from each of the system at time intervals of 5, 10, 15, 30, 60,120, 240,360 min and analyzed for drug content using UV spectrophotometer ³³.

Skin permeation studies

In-vitro skin permeation studies were carried out for the best four formulations that showed higher drug release through dialysis membrane-70, using the rat abdominal skin. The rat skin was obtained from the abdominal portion of an albino rat after sacrificing the animal. The hair and the fat were removed after treating the skin with 0.32 mol /l ammonia solution for 30 min. The excised rat skin was washed with receptor medium, tied to the Franz diffusion cell (donor cell) having a diffusion area of 3.8 cm² and 100cm height, so that the stratum corneum side of the skin was in intimate contact with the release surface of the formulation in the donor cell. All experiments were carried out in triplicate. A weighed quantity of formulation equivalent to 1g of the drug was placed onto the rat skin and was immersed slightly in 100ml of receptor medium (phosphate buffer pH 6.8 for the formulations of coriander aqueous extract and mixture of ethanol: phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (60:40) for the formulations of coriander oil) which was continuously stirred and the temperature was maintained at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Aliquots of 1ml were withdrawn from each of the system at time intervals of 5, 10, 15, 30, 60,120, 240,360 min and analyzed for drug content using UV spectrophotometer ³⁵.

Drug release kinetics

To study the release kinetics of the formulations, the data obtained from *invitro* release studies were plotted in various kinetic models.

Zero order as cumulative amount of drug released vs. time (equation 1)

$$C=K_0 t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where, K_0 is the zero order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time and t is the time in hours. A graph of concentration vs. time with a slope equal to K_0 and intercept the origin of axes.

First order as log cumulative percent drug remaining vs. time (equation 2)

$$\text{Log } C = \text{Log } C_0 - k t/2.303 \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where, C_0 is the initial concentration of the drug, k is the first order rate constant and t is the time in hours.

Higuchi's model as the cumulative percentage of drug released vs. square root of the time (equation 3).

$$Q=K \cdot \sqrt{t} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where, K is the constant reflecting the design variables of the system and t is the time in hours. Hence drug release rate is reciprocal of square root of time^{6,13}.

Statistical Analysis

One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to identify the significant difference in percent drug release of the optimized formulations with and without the addition of penetration enhancer.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Antibacterial activity of extract and coriander oil

The extract and oil of coriander were examined for their antibacterial activity against *P.acne* and *S. epidermidis*. The results revealed that both the extract as well as oil inhibit the growth of *P.acne* and *S. epidermidis*. Aqueous extract showed the antibacterial effect with a zone of inhibition of 21.5 ± 1.4 and 20.6 ± 1.09 mm against *P.acne* and *S. epidermidis* respectively (Table 1). The MIC values of 1.7 mg/ml and 2.1 mg/ml were obtained for aqueous extract against *P.acne* and *S. epidermidis* respectively. But the coriander oil showed the greater zone of inhibition (31.4 ± 2.5 and 28.1 ± 2.4 mm for *P. acne* and *S.epidermidis*) and lesser MIC (1 and 1.1% against *P.acne* and *S. epidermidis* respectively) as compared to the extract.

Antimicrobial activity of formulations

The incorporation of penetration enhancer increased the antimicrobial activity of both types of formulations (Table 2). Due to the effect of menthol the antimicrobial activity of F_{011} became comparable to that of the Clindamycin phosphate against *P. acne*. This enhancement in the diameter of the zone of inhibition on the addition of menthol is the outcome of its synergistic effect with the drug against acne inducing bacteria.

Drug content

The formulations were developed from aqueous extract (F_{a1}), oil (F_{o1}), aqueous extract with penetration enhancer (F_{a11}) and oil with penetration enhancer (F_{o11}) and subjected to the drug content studies. The drug content of the formulations with aqueous extract increased from 94.5(F_{a1}) to 97.9% (F_{a11}) and that of the oil

A

B

C

Fig 5. : Release Kinetic model for optimized formulation of coriander Oil.

A: Zero order release kinetic model, B: First order release kinetic model, C: Higuchi model.

B

C
Fig 6. : Release Kinetic model for optimized formulation of extract with penetration enhancer.

A: Zero order release kinetic model, B: First order release kinetic model, C: Higuchi model

A B

C
Fig 7: Release Kinetic model for optimized formulation of oil with penetration enhancer.
A: Zero order release kinetic model, B: First order release kinetic model, C: Higuchi model

formulations increased from 96.5 (F₀₁) to 98.9% (F₀₁₁) as evident from Table 3. The increase in the drug content is due to the presence of penetration enhancer. The values of drug content showed that no degradation of the drug occurred during the process.

Invitro diffusion and permeation

The *invitro* diffusion studies revealed that the formulations with menthol showed enhanced release of 96.8% (F_{a11}) and 98.2% (F_{o11}). These results of *invitro* diffusion further lead to the conduction of permeation studies. The results of skin permeation studies conducted for 6hrs showed that maximum amount of drug permeated through the skin during 6 hrs was 90% for F_{a1} which rise to 95.8% for F_{a11} (Table 3). So the permeation of the drug increased after the incorporation of menthol into the formulation of aqueous extract as is also shown in (Fig 1). The same pattern of result was observed for oil formulations as the maximum amount of drug permeated through skin during 6hrs was 91.5% for F_{o1} which increased to 97.7% for F_{o11} as evidenced in the Fig 2. This precisely showed that the addition of permeation enhancer increases the permeation of the drug through the skin¹¹.

The flux was obtained by dividing the cumulative amount of the drug permeated per cm² of the skin with time. The flux of the formulations also increased with addition of penetration enhancer, menthol [8,11] as corresponding flux value increased from 44.6±1.05µg/cm²hr⁻¹ to 74.4±2.09µg/cm²hr⁻¹ for aqueous formulations with and without penetration enhancer and from 49.6±1.09µg/cm²hr⁻¹ to 85.8±2.2µg/cm²hr⁻¹ for oil formulations with and without penetration enhancer respectively. These values of flux indicate that the drugs will dwell at the site of acne lesion and will reach to the follicles.

The observations revealed that oil formulation having penetration enhancer (F_{o11}) has greater permeation as compared to the aqueous formulation having penetration enhancer (F_{a11}) (Fig 3). This is ascribed to the fact that terpenes, present in the volatile oil, initially have the property to enhance the permeation through the skin. This property is further supplemented by the addition of penetration enhancer, menthol, to the formulation.

Interpretation of statistical analysis:

The calculated F values (179 and 195.5) obtained separately from statistical analysis of aqueous extract formulations F_{a1} and F_{a11} and oil formulations F_{o1} and F_{o11} were more than that of table value (4.96) at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis was rejected (Table 5,6). There was significant difference between the % drugs released from the formulations formulated with penetration enhancer.

Release kinetic studies

The *invitro* diffusion data of the formulations of coriander extract was subjected to kinetic analysis. The selection criteria (R²) and the equations best describing the kinetics of *invitro* drug release are given in Tables [4]. The release of the drug from all the formulations was found to follow the first order release kinetics. The results are in agreement with the previous investigation performed by Dua et.al (2011). This implies that the release is concentration dependent. Higher correlation, as indicated by R², was observed for the higuichi matrix release kinetics in the optimized formulation (Fig 4,5,6,7), suggesting diffusion as a probable prominent mechanism of drug release. In diffusion, the rate of drug dissolution within the matrix must be much higher than that of the diffusion rate of the drug leaving the matrix. This may be attributed to the nature of gelling agent used.

Table 5: Statistical analysis of aq. formulations

Source of information	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of squares	Calculated F value	Tabulated F value
Between sum of squares	157.56	1	157.5	179	4.97
Error sum of squares	8.79	10	0.879		
Total	166.35	11			

Table 6: Statistical analysis of oil formulations

Source of information	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of squares	Calculated F value	Tabulated F value
Between sum of squares	105	1	105.6	195	4.97
Error sum of squares	5.4	10	0.54		
Total	110.4	11			

The incorporation of penetration enhancer, menthol, increased both the antibacterial activity of the formulation more than that of the crude drug and the significant permeation of drug to the desired site of action.

Conclusion

The addition of penetration enhancer, menthol, increased the permeation of the drugs. The antibacterial activity of coriander oil was found to be more so they can be further used for development of advanced anti acne formulations. Aqueous extract is also a good option to be considered.

Author's Contribution

AV: The main author involved in the literature survey, compilation and acquisition of data, planning design and carrying out research work, interpretation of data and along with review of intellectual content and drafting of the final manuscript titled **“Comparative study and analysis of release kinetics of coriander formulations”**. PS: research guide who gave valuable suggestions from time to time to carry out the research work properly.

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